

Evaluation of mixed adsorbents for the removal of arsenic(III) from wastewater

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Abstract : Utilization of red mud and its (1 : 1) mixture by weight with haematite, china clay, fly ash and china clay-fly ash mixed adsorbents has been made for the removal of arsenic(III) from waste water at different operating parameter such as adsorbate and adsorbent dose, particle size of adsorbent and agitation speed. The percentage removal of As^{III} has been found optimum at lower concentration and increase in adsorbent dose and decrease in particle size at 220 rpm of agitation speed.

Keywords : As^{III}, adsorption, mixed adsorbents, particle size, agitation speed.

Introduction

It is well known that arsenic is a natural constituent of earth crust and it is reached in the environment through weathering and volcanic eruption and escaping of suspended particulates and aerosols through water and air. The environmental pollution is the most remarkable side effect of the rapid industrialization and growing population of the world. Water is an important constituent of environment as well as the most essential requirement for human beings, animals and plants. Heavy metal combination in aquatic environment has increased the awareness due to its toxicity. The concentration of arsenic/heavy metals in various industrial wastewater may also vary considerably both in quality and quantity. The heavy metal pollutants cause direct toxicity effect both to humans and aquatic biota due to their presence beyond specified limits. Arsenic emission originates¹⁻³ from industrial activities and operations such as, effluent of explosive, fertilizers, pesticides, herbicides, pharmaceuticals, metallurgical mixing, ceramic and cement industries. It also accounts for widespread contamination of soil and ground water environment. On staying in atmosphere arsenic circulates in natural ecosystems for a long time depending on the prevailing geochemical environment. It exists in several allotropic forms and in different oxida-

tion state. The most common is gray crystalline with low heat and electrical conductivity. It is so widely distributed and its traces can be detected almost everywhere. Arsenic and its compounds have some used based on chemical or physical properties, but over 80% of the consumption in recent years has depended on some applications of its toxic properties. Arsenic causes carcinogenic effect on living beings. Toxicity of arsenic produces injury⁴ once it reaches a susceptible site in an organism and damages skin, lungs, gastrointestinal and nasopharyngeal system.

The aim of the undertaking work is to suggest a simple and cheap treatment methods for the abatement of As^{III} level in the effluents coming out of the conventional treatment plant handling composite wastewater. In the present investigation adsorption process through batch mode operation is chosen as treatment technique for removal of arsenic from water bodies/industrial effluents. This technique is more advanced and viable over a variety of process used for treatment of wastewater. The adsorbents red mud (RM) and its mixture (in 1 : 1 ratio by weight) with haematite (HM), china clay (CC), fly ash (FA) and 1 : 1 mixture of china clay with fly ash were used for the removal of As^{III}. These adsorbents are nonconventional, cheap, easily available and having no disposal problem.

Materials and method :

The adsorbents were obtained from various parts of our country and mixed adsorbents were prepared by mixing in 1 : 1 proportion by weight. The occurrence and physical and chemical characterization of adsorbents were made by using the methods reported earlier⁵. X-Ray diffractograms of the adsorbents were obtained by a Rigaku, X-RD spectrophotometer using a copper target for determining the nature of mineral phase present in the adsorbent particle.

The batch mode operation was carried out by shaking one gram of adsorbent with 50 ml of aqueous solution of As^{III} of desired initial concentration, temperature and pH in 250 ml glass bottle in a shaking thermostat at a constant speed of 220 rpm. The amount of adsorption was determined at different time intervals till the attainment of the equilibrium. The suspension was taken out as soon as equilibrium was achieved. It was then centrifused and the supernatant liquid was analyzed spectrophotometrically^{6,7} (UV-Vis spectrophotometer 118 Systronics) to find out the residual adsorbate concentration at 520 nm. The pH of the aqueous solution of arsenic was adjusted using HCl and NaOH.

Results and discussion

Characterisation of adsorbents :

Alumina is the major constituents of all adsorbents are already reported⁸. Red mud and haematite posses trace amount of silica while china clay and fly ash contain very trace of iron oxide. X-Ray diffraction data of all adsorbents with respect to their corresponding *d*-values, 2θ values and intensity of peaks conclude that red mud (Table 1) is mainly composed of kaolinite, natrolite, rutile, haematite, tridymite, geothite, bothemite. Red mud and china clay (1 : 1) is mainly made up of kaolinite, natrolite, rutile, haematite, α-quartz, tridymite, geothite, bothemite. The mixed adsorbent red mud-fly ash (1 : 1) posses the mineral morphology of haematite rutile, α-quartz, tridymite, kaolinite while china clay-fly ash (1 : 1) has kaolinite, α-quartz, haematite, tridymite. Red mud-haematite (1 : 1) (Table 2) is mainly composed of haematite, kaolinite, rutile, tridymite, bothemite, α-quartz, etc.

Effects of concentration :

The contact time between arsenic solution and adsorbent plays a significant role in the process of removal.

Table 1. X-Ray diffraction data of red mud

Intensity	2θ	<i>d</i> -values
20	18.26	4.855
29	21.32	4.164
23	25.24	3.526
100	27.27	3.268
52	27.63	3.226
24	28.12	3.171
16	29.44	3.032
27	33.13	2.702
44	35.67	2.515
14	36.08	2.487
24	37.14	2.419
18	38.27	2.350
35	39.31	2.290
15	40.88	2.206
10	47.90	1.898
8	48.48	1.876
17	49.50	1.840
30	52.22	1.750
28	54.03	1.696
22	64.02	1.453

Kaolinite, Natrolite, Rutile, Haematite, Tridymite, Geothite, Bothemite.

Table 2. X-Ray diffraction data of red mud-haematite (1 : 1)

Intensity	2θ	<i>d</i> -values
29.6	24.102	3.6894
27.0	27.317	3.2621
100	33.128	2.7020
16.8	34.361	2.6078
49.7	35.624	2.5182
27.5	49.423	1.8426
30.6	54.053	1.6952
20.5	57.507	1.6013
40.1	62.414	1.4867
21.9	63.956	1.4545

Kaolinite, Rutile, Tridymite, Bothemite, Haematite, α-Quartz.

The time required to reach equilibrium is longer for more porous adsorbents like activated carbon and polymeric

materials and shorter in the case of relatively less porous or non-porous adsorbents such as china clay, haematite, fly ash, red mud, silica, wollastonite etc. In physical adsorption most of the adsorbate species are adsorbed on the interface within a short interval of contact time. However, strong chemical binding of adsorbate with adsorbent requires a longer contact time for the attainment of equilibrium. A review of the available literature on adsorption at the solid-solution interface reveals that the uptake of adsorbate species is fast at the initial stage of the contact period and becomes slower near the equilibrium. This is obvious from the fact that a large number of surface sites are available for adsorption at the initial stages and after a lapse of time, the remaining surface sites are difficult to be occupied because of repulsion⁹ between the solute molecules of the solid and bulk phases.

The effect of initial arsenic concentration on the removal efficiency of adsorbent and time to reach equilibrium were experimentally studied over a wide range of arsenic concentration (2.5–10 mg/L) for all the adsorbents

used. All other parameters (agitation speed, adsorbent dose, particle size) were kept same and pH was maintained at the respective optimum value. The effect of initial arsenic(III) concentration and contact time for various systems are measured and the summary of the findings are given in Table 3. It is quite obvious from results that at all concentrations of adsorbate species the extent of adsorption in each case increases rapidly from the initial stages followed by a gradual increase till the equilibrium is attained and thereafter the extent of removal remains constant for a long time of contact. The equilibrium time for all the adsorbents under investigation was observed to be independent of initial arsenic concentration. These results further indicate that the saturation time remains unchanged with the change in concentration of arsenic solutions. The efficiency of adsorbents for the removal of As^{III} from their aqueous solutions under the similar condition of concentration, temperature and pH is in the following order : Red mud > china clay-fly ash (1 : 1) > red mud-china clay (1 : 1) > red mud-fly ash

Table 3. Effect of initial concentration on the removal of As^{III}

Adsorbent dose = 20 g/L, Temp. = 30 ± 0.1 °C, pH = 8.0, Particle size < 53 µm, Agitation speed = 220 rpm

Adsorbent	Initial concentration (mg/L)	Removal (%)	Amount adsorbed (mg/g)	Equilibrium time (min)
Red mud	2.5	93.0	0.1163	140
	5.0	86.0	0.2150	
	7.5	72.0	0.2700	
	10.0	67.0	0.3300	
China clay-fly ash (1 : 1)	2.5	90.0	0.1125	120
	5.0	85.0	0.2125	
	7.5	69.0	0.2588	
	10.0	66.0	0.3300	
Red mud-haematite (1 : 1)	2.5	85.0	0.1063	100
	5.0	79.0	0.1975	
	7.5	73.0	0.2738	
	10.0	56.0	0.2800	
Red mud-china clay (1 : 1)	2.5	88.0	0.1100	140
	5.0	81.0	0.2025	
	7.5	67.0	0.2513	
	10.0	62.0	0.3100	
Red mud-fly ash (1 : 1)	2.5	87.0	0.1088	120
	5.0	80.0	0.2000	
	7.5	65.5	0.2456	
	10.0	61.0	0.3050	

(1 : 1) > red mud-haematite (1 : 1).

An uniform, smooth and continuous adsorption behavior tending to saturation suggests the possibility of formation of monolayer coverage on the surface of adsorbents. Similar observations¹⁰ have been reported by several workers for adsorption of heavy metals on fly ash, china clay, wollastonite and red mud. The arsenic uptake per unit mass of the adsorbent increases with increase in the initial concentration. However, the percentage removal increases with decrease in initial concentration for all adsorbents. The different oxides of silicon, aluminium, iron and calcium, which are major constituents of adsorbents used here and water molecules present in the vicinity of these oxides play an important role in the removal of adsorbate species, from aqueous solution by adsorption process. When the adsorbents brought into intimate contact with the water dipoles, a redistribution of charges and potential take place at solid solution interface. The electrochemical potential of the charge carried in both phases becomes equal at equilibrium and an electrical double layer is formed due to non distribution of charge and potential. The electrical and electrochemical properties of the double layer are influenced by various physico-chemical properties of the bulk phase. Adsorbents from oxides-water interface, when put in water and H^+ and OH^- ions becomes the constituent parts of the oxide of adsorbents, a state of thermodynamic reversibility exists at the surface of adsorbents. The H^+ and OH^- ions are thus, potential determining ions with respect to hydroxylate/oxide and the mechanism of adsorption is decided by surface hydroxylation and its subsequent acid-base dissociation at oxide-solution interface. The negative charge density lies on the oxygen site of the surface favouring cationic adsorption whereas the positive charge density lies on the metal sites of the oxide surface which is favourable for anionic adsorption. Similar type of mechanism has also been suggested¹¹ by for double layer model of adsorption of anions at the oxides-solution interface. The removal of As^{III} at various concentrations and retention times are satisfactorily explained by above mechanism. The surface reaction of adsorbate ions and its species owing to adsorption decreases with lapse of retention time and ultimately reaches to equilibrium. A more appropriate double layer model for interpreting the mechanism of adsorption of adsorbate species at the solid solu-

tion interface has been suggested the following equilibria established at the surface (s) and in the bulk (b) of the solution :

where MOH stands for a multivalent metal hydroxide.

Effect of adsorbent dose :

Adsorbent dose on As^{III} uptake infers that there is a significant increase in % of As^{3+} removal (48 to 94%) on increasing adsorbent dose from 10 to 50 g/L in each case having same experimental conditions at pH 8.0. The results are shown in Fig. 1 for red mud. Similar observations were found with all adsorbent mixture and values at equilibrium are reported in Table 4. Increasing in the percentage removal and decrease in amount adsorbed per unit weight of adsorbent is very natural because adsorption is a surface phenomena¹² and higher the amount of adsorbent more is the adsorbate removed from solution. It is also due to irregular faces, edges and laminar regions of adsorptive sites of metallic oxides which have different residential valencies and adsorptive potentials.

Effect of particle size :

The influence of particle size furnishes important information for achieving optimum utilization of adsorbent. In heavy metal removal process, the adsorbent particle size has significant influence on the adsorption time and kinetics of adsorption. Rates of adsorption on a solid surface are expected to vary with available surface area for a constant adsorbent mass with particle size. The adsorption capacity is directly proportional to the total exposed surface and inversely proportional to the particle diameter for the adsorbents. The presence of a large number of smaller particles¹³ provides the sorption system with a greater surface area available for arsenic removal. The effect of increasing the surface area is to increase slightly the intraparticle rate parameter.

The influences of adsorbent particle size were investigated during three particle sizes (53, 124 and 178 μm) under identical conditions of initial concentration, adsorbent dose and temperature. The pH of solution was main-

Fig. 1. Time variation of As^{III} adsorption on china clay-fly ash at different adsorption doses.

Condition : conc. = 5.0 mg/L, particle size = < 53 μm, Temp. = 30 °C and pH = 8.0.

tained at the respective optimum value. The plot of amount of As^{III} adsorbed versus contact time at different sizes of adsorbents are observed and the results at equilibrium condition are listed in Table 5. It is evident from the table that as the particle size decreases the percentage removal and uptake of arsenic(III) increases. However, this increase in uptake of arsenic with increase in particle size is marginal which may be due to the narrow range of the particle size of the adsorbent used. The particle size was found to have little effect on the adsorption process. The

weak effect of particle size upon adsorption equilibrium time is related to the fact that all adsorption surfaces can be considered as result of internal effects.

Effect of agitation speed :

In fluid-particle system, the rate of adsorption is controlled either by the film diffusion or pore diffusion depending upon the degree of agitation. At lower agitation speed, liquid film around the adsorbent particles is thicker and film diffusion is the rate limiting step and mass transfer of adsorbate to the external surface of particle is slow.

Table 4. Effect of adsorbent dose on the removal of As^{III}

As^{III} concentration = 10 mg/L, Temp. = 30 ± 0.1 °C, pH = 8.0

Adsorbent	Adsorbent dose (g/L)	Removal (%)	Amount adsorbed (mg/g)
Red mud	10	60.5	0.605
	20	67.0	0.335
	30	79.0	0.263
	40	87.0	0.218
	50	94.0	0.188
China clay-fly ash (1 : 1)	10	58.0	0.580
	20	66.0	0.330
	30	78.0	0.260
	40	85.0	0.213
	50	91.0	0.182
Red mud-haematite (1 : 1)	10	48.0	0.480
	20	56.0	0.280
	30	63.0	0.210
	40	71.0	0.178
	50	80.0	0.160
Red mud-china clay (1 : 1)	10	57.0	0.570
	20	62.0	0.310
	30	70.0	0.233
	40	77.0	0.193
	50	89.0	0.178
Red mud-fly ash (1 : 1)	10	54.0	0.540
	20	61.0	0.305
	30	69.0	0.230
	40	76.0	0.190
	50	84.0	0.168

Table 5. Effect of particle size on the removal of As^{III}

Adsorbent dose = 20 g/L, Temp. = 30 ± 0.1 °C, pH = 8.0, As^{III} concentration = 10 mg/L

Adsorbent	Particle size (µm)	Removal (%)	Amount adsorbed (mg/g)
Red mud	53	93.00	0.1163
	124	85.50	0.1069
	178	72.50	0.0906
China clay-fly ash (1 : 1)	53	90.00	0.1125
	124	84.50	0.1056
	178	80.00	0.1000
Red mud-haematite (1 : 1)	53	85.00	0.1063
	124	81.00	0.1013
	178	77.00	0.0963
Red mud-china clay (1 : 1)	53	88.00	0.1100
	124	85.00	0.1063
	178	81.63	0.1020
Red mud-fly ash (1 : 1)	53	87.00	0.1088
	124	82.50	0.1031
	178	74.00	0.0925

At higher agitation speed, the film diffusion increases to a maximum value and pore diffusion becomes the rate controlling step. The effect of agitation speed on the uptake of As^{III} on to adsorbents used was studied by varying the agitation speed from 150 to 300 rpm keeping the concentration, pH, temperature and other parameters constant throughout. The result obtained are illustrated graphically in Fig. 2. The maximum percentage removal of As with regard to specific adsorption capacity at equilibrium condition are found to be 87-93% at 300 rpm for all adsorbents, while at 150 rpm removal is observed 56-63%.

The results indicate that there is a definite gradual improvement in the extent of adsorption with increase in the speed of agitation. It has been supported^{14,15} by the report that there is an increase in the intraparticle diffusion parameter with an increase in the agitation rate. The effect on the macropore was greater than that on the micropore parameter which remains essentially constant. The increase in external fluid velocity causes a decrease in the external surface film resistance allowing the arsenic effluent to reach the particle surface more rapidly. This in turn, may provide a greater driving force¹⁶ for intraparticle diffusion. The effect of increasing stirring

Fig. 2. Time variation of As^{III} adsorption on china clay-fly ash at different agitation speeds.

Condition : conc. = 5.0 mg/L, particle size = < 53 μm, Temp. = 30 °C and pH = 8.0.

rate is to decrease the boundary layer thickness and hence the film resistance to mass transfer surrounding the adsorbent particles.

Conclusions :

X-Ray diffraction study represents of bothemite, natrolite, rutile, kaolinite, hematite, α -quartz, tridymite, goethite minerals in the adsorbents. The removal of As^{III} from the solution of different concentrations is rapid in initial stages followed by slow adsorption near saturation. The percentage removal of As^{III} is found to increase with decrease in solute concentration, increase in adsorbent dose and decrease in particle size. A rapid uptake of adsorbate and establishment of equilibrium in a short period signifies the efficiency of the adsorbent for its use in wastewater treatment. The adsorption of As^{III} on different adsorbents is to be in following order : RM > CC-FA > RM-CC > RM-FA > RM-HM. Increase in speed of agitation does not show appreciable effect on the removal of As^{III} after 220 rpm. The equilibrium time is independent of initial adsorbate concentration and agitation speed indicating adsorption predominates on the outer surface of particles.

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